

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 – Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.15 Annual report on external communications for impact assessment January 2024- December 2024

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Document History

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Abstract

The main aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality and harmonisation of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicines use in pregnancy and during breastfeeding.

The 5.3 sub-task aim is to engage HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public to stimulate pregnancy reporting through PV systems, by increasing their awareness that they can play an active role in increasing general knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The objective of this report is to summarize communication actions performed in WP5 to disseminate knowledge about medicines use during pregnancy and lactation and to engage pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals (HCPs) in the ConcePTION ecosystem between January 2024 and December 2024. The communications actions may have different targets and different messages.

For this report on the last year of the project, the main communication activities were related to engage key stakeholders in the ConcePTION ecosystem and to increase awareness on knowledge bank and to prepare sustainability plan implementation.

Any communications in December 2024 were not included due to finalization date of this report.

Methods

The objective of the report is to make an inventory of communication actions performed in WP5 on the fifth year of the project.

The communication actions are classified by their objective:

- Engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem and to stimulate reporting on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding.
- Increase awareness on knowledge bank.

The communications actions are grouped by objective and are described using the following parameters: the geographical reach, the target audience, the channel used, the date of dissemination, and the main presenter.

Results

The communication actions for this report are divided into:

- Targeted actions to engage women and to stimulate reporting on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding
- Targeted actions to increase awareness on knowledge bank
- Targeted actions to prepare sustainability plan

The ConcePTION project channels include a project website (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>) a Twitter account, a YouTube channel, a LinkedIn account, and an e-mail newsletter. On X (ex-Twitter) (<https://X.com/IMIConcePTION>), we are followed by 559 users (as of December 2024) with organic reach through their networks. In 2024, our reach on the platform dropped as many users left X, but the engagement rate has stayed high (over 5%). The project's newsletter audience is building through project events, and currently reaches 700+ subscribers, representing a wide variety of stakeholders. Through forwards, we are also reaching the subscribers' networks. On average, newsletters reach 400 non-subscribers, with a high level of engagement (measured by clicks on links). On LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception/>), the project has 830 followers, with a wide organic reach, where posts had 56,454 impressions and 1,731 reactions in the last 12 months.. YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@imiconception6542>) is primarily used as a video repository, and with 66 subscribers, we have registered 6,730 views of the 44 published videos since the launch in February 2020.

Actions to engage women in the ConcePTION ecosystem and to stimulate reporting were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations. The communications actions to engage women have been conducted ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (X campaigns (<https://X.com/IMIConcePTION>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/news/>), workshop and webinars, etc).

Table 1: Communication actions to engage women and to stimulate reporting of exposure during pregnancy and breastfeeding

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on need to explore paternal exposure)	February 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on launch of studies on the safety of medicines during breastfeeding)	April 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Webinar on ConcePTION and LifeSaver joining forces to improve maternal health and pregnancy pharmacovigilance	May 2024	Myriam Sturkenboom, Marjolein Willemen, Pieter Annaert, Jasper Levink
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in X.com on key facts about use of medicines in pregnancy and during breastfeeding)	August 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in X.com on update on studies on the safety of medicines during pregnancy)	October 2024	Myriam Sturkenboom, Marjolein Willemen, Pieter Annaert, Jasper Levink
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on access to trusted information)	May 2024	Safe Motherhood week
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in LX.com on access to trusted information)	May 2024	Safe Motherhood week

Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on e-learning package for health care professionals)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on reassuring breast milk study results)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in X.com on reassuring breast milk study results)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on preventing side effects during pregnancy as part of medsafetyweek)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on preventing side effects during pregnancy as part of medsafetyweek)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in X.com on preventing side effects during pregnancy as part of medsafetyweek)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on Meds4Mums2B mobile app)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post X.com on Meds4Mums2B mobile app)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in LinkedIn to stimulate reporting as part of medsafetyweek)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on ConcePTION closing event))	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in LinkedIn on ConcePTION closing event)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION, IHI, and event participants
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on ConcePTION data pipeline webinar))	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in LinkedIn on ConcePTION data pipeline webinar)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION

The communications actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank have been conducted by task 5.3 members with support of ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (X

campaigns (<https://X.com/IMIConception>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/news/>), workshop, and face to face presentations, etc).

Table 2: Communication actions to increase awareness on knowledge bank

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on data harmonization in pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	February 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on data harmonization in pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	February 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in X.com announcing upcoming MUMS)	May 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on MUMS launch)	June 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on MUMS launch)	June 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Consortium participants	MUMS launch at ConcePTION General assembly meeting (face to face)	June 2024	Miranda Van Tuyl
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in X.com on MUMS launch)	June & July 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Teratology specialists	ConcePTION update and lessons learned at ENTIS OTIS joint meeting (face to face)	September 2024	Benedikte Cuppers & Fergal O'shaugnessy
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Webinar on MUMS knowledge bank and e-learning for health professionals	October 2024	Miranda Van Tuyl, Fergal O'shaugnessy and Brian Cleary
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in X.com on MUMS knowledge bank and e-learning for health professionals)	October 2024	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (posts in LinkedIn on MUMS knowledge bank and e-learning for health professionals)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION and WP5

The communications actions to prepare sustainability plan implementation have been conducted by WP5 members with support of WP6 and WP8 through workshop, and face to face presentations with various stakeholders.

Table 3: Communication actions to prepare sustainability plan implementation

Country/ Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, HCP organizations, Government, patient organizations	MUMS stakeholder event (face to face workshop)	Sept 2024	WP5 and WP6
Global	Women, HCP organizations, Government, patient organizations	Face to face meeting with WHO-UMC	Sept 2024	WP5
Global	Women, HCP organizations, Government, patient organizations	ConcePTION closing event (face to face meeting)	November 2024	IMI ConcePTION and WP5 booth

Discussion and Conclusion

In the last year of the project, the communication efforts were focused on engaging women, raising awareness on medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding and stimulating reporting as well as engaging new stakeholders to prepare sustainability plan implementation.